

PSYCHOLOGICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF ETHNIC AND SOCIAL TOLERANCE

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Abstract. *In the era of globalization and informatization processes, tolerance has been one of the current socio-psychological and insular maummo. At the moment, tolerance, as a moral norm, presupposes that for the successful development of all mankind, it will be the main and necessary factor in the formation of the characteristics of the individuality of each individual, the ability to tolerate situations arising through the types of tolerance and stress.*

Keywords: *tolerance, trait, ethnic, psychocorrection, social, tolerance, socio-cultural, personality, perception.*

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОЯВЛЕНИЯ ЭТНИЧЕСКОЙ И СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ

Аннотация. *В эпоху процессов глобализации и информатизации толерантность стала одним из актуальных социально-психологических и замкнутых мауммо. На данный момент толерантность, как моральная норма, предполагает, что для успешного развития всего человечества она будет главным и необходимым фактором формирования характеристик индивидуальности каждого индивида, способности переносить ситуации, возникающие благодаря видам толерантности и стрессу.*

Ключевые слова: *толерантность, черта, этническая, психокоррекция, социальная, толерантность, социокультурная, личность, восприятие.*

2017 marked a new stage in the historical development and development of Uzbekistan. The president of this year is Sh. On the side of Mirziyoyev, the so-called "Year of dialogue with the people and human interests", the tasks set out in the "strategy of action in the five creative directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" clearly demonstrated how protected human interests are in our society. 5.1 priority areas in the field of security, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance and deeply thought out, mutually beneficial and practical foreign policy in the fifth priority area of action strategy. Priority areas in the field of security, religious tolerance and ensuring interethnic harmony: protection of the constitutional order, sovereignty, territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan; ensuring information security and improving the information protection system, timely and worthy resistance to threats in the information field; strengthening civil, interethnic and interdenominational peace and harmony; strengthening the defense capabilities of the state, increasing the combat power and potential of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan; preventing environmental problems that harm the environment, Population Health and gene pool; the improvement of the system for the prevention and elimination of emergency situations, such as the provision of a person, his peace, health, bright perspective, is the most important thing in all these days, showing how important it is to form and develop social tolerance, especially in young girls of teenage age, who are now stepping into an independent life.

The educational system is of particular importance in instilling ideas of tolerance in the minds of young people, because it is they who master the social experiences and values

accumulated in educational institutions on a scientific basis and in a systematic way. Also, due to the interdependence between the stages of the educational system, evolutionism is ensured in the process of upbringing. The education system serves to prevent the emergence of any nationalistic feelings in them, such as the superiority of one's own nationality, religion over another, in order to make decisions about national pride, love for the motherland, feelings of nationalism in young people. The occurrence of such feelings in young people leads to conflicts between nations, religious conflicts can.

The main task in the formation of the social tolerance of the individual is to expand its social-role relations, to accept the diversity in the social life of society and to elevate the culture of communication in entering into effective interaction with representatives of different social groups.

Tolerance is not a phenomenon that appears today or yesterday. This quality has been absorbed into the blood and blood of our people for centuries. Tolerance has deep historical roots. For example, if we take the life of countries on the Great Silk Road or the Timurid era, it is well known from history books that representatives of different nationalities and nationalities took part in the construction of majestic buildings.

Even today, maintaining and strengthening tolerance has become the top priority of state policy, creating legal conditions for the preservation and development of the language, culture, customs and traditions of all nations and elates. Today, the focus is on further strengthening mutual affection among different nations in our country.

The results of the study obtained on the basis of the correctional program on the methodology of the G.Saldatova "personality tolerance index"

G.The following statistics were obtained from students under the saldatova tolerance determination index methodology.

During the study, after conducting socio-psychological training sessions, students of academic lyceums were analyzed what changes have occurred in the quality of tolerance. The results of the study showed a number of changes after the application of a psychocorrectional program.

The average quantitative values of the results obtained according to the state of the methodology before and after the training program were compared. According to him, our experiences, we can see that “ethnic tolerance” is the highest result sum score 15% average level accumulated data 31% low accumulated score 54%. This is a change in the way that our results on the basis of the correctional program, which develops the qualities of tolerance carried by us, are as follows. Low level 25% average level 48% high level 27%. This can be seen to have given the program efficiency.

Thus, the analysis of the philosophical and psychological and pedagogical literature on this issue allowed us to draw the following conclusions: the general methodological principle of studying the phenomenon of tolerance is the principle of humanism, since tolerance does not accept violence, cruelty, aggression. freedom of personality; tolerance is the manifestation of human freedom as the ability to make meaningful, responsible and free choice of one's own views on "others". Tolerance is possible on the basis of communication with other points of view and points of view as a special way of relationships and interactions between people. Tolerance is formed on the basis of the socio-cultural experience of the people and is manifested in different forms and boundaries; culture serves as the axiological basis of tolerance.

The roots of tolerance go back to ancient history. From the time of Zoroastrianism to the modern period, it also made it possible to formulate the existence of tolerance concepts in our conclusions: tolerance in a person initially forms in the family, and later, develops in preschool educational organizations, schools, technical schools, lyceums, higher educational institutions. The fact that a person perceives the variety of life, the variety of people, groups and the fact that they all deserve to be respected, and perceives it as it is, is an indicator of high culture and spirituality.

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